

revealed isometric particles about 50 nm in diameter having spikes, but no other virus-like particles. The RRSV-like particles from China reacted positively with the antiserum of RRSV from the Philippines in both the immunoelectron microscopy and ELISA. We concluded that the rice ragged stunt disease in China is caused by a virus morphologically and serologically similar to that in the Philippines. ■

Report of 1978 Rice Tungro Virus Collaborative Project

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The life span and tungro transmission of viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on seedlings of 10 rice varieties were collaboratively studied at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, India, the IRRI, and Lembaga Penelitian Pertanian (LPP), Indonesia. The objective was to use the varieties as differentials for determining the existence of biotypes of the tungro vector and strains of the tungro virus.

On the basis of life span, the ability of the tungro vector to attack the 10 varieties was similar at the 4 locations. The test varieties were unable to separate the biotypes of the tungro vector in the four locations. The arbitrary classification based on average life span placed Gam Pai 30-12-15, IR34, and Ptb 18 in the resistant group; Latisail and Pankhari 203 in the intermediate group; and Ambemohar 159, Habiganj DW8, IR26, Kataribhog, and TN1 in the susceptible group. However, Ambemohar 159 was in the intermediate group at AICRIP but in the susceptible group at the other locations. Pankhari 203 was susceptible at CRRI, but intermediate at the other locations (see table). Hence, these two varieties could be used to show the slight difference in tungro vector biotypes between AICRIP and CRRI.

On the basis of tungro transmission and seedling infection, the averages

Reactions of 10 rice varieties to tungro-viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* and to tungro virus on the basis of an arbitrary classification system at 4 locations, 1978.

Variety	Reaction ^a to vector (left letter) and virus (right)				
	AICRIP	CKRI	IRRI	LPP	Mean
TN1	SS	SS	SS	SS	SS
IR26	SI	SS	SS	SS	SS
Ambemohar 159	IS	SI	SI	SI	SI
Habiganj DW8	SS	SR	SR	SR	SR
Kataribhog	II	SR	SR	SR	SR
Latisail	II	SS	SS	SI	IS
Pankhari 203	II	SI	IR	IR	IR
IR34	II	IS	RS	II	RS
Gam Pai 30-1 2-15	RI	IR	RI	II	RI
Ptb 18	IS	RR	RI	RI	RI

^aK, I, and S indicate resistant, intermediate, and susceptible. The underscoring indicates striking difference from others.

support the arbitrary classification of Habiganj DW8, Pankhari 203, and Kataribhog in the group resistant to the tungro virus; Ambemohar 159, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and Ptb 18 in the intermediate group; and IR26, IR34, Latisail, and TN1 in the susceptible group (see table). However, variations occurred among the locations, particularly at AICRIP where none of the varieties could be put in the resistant group. Habiganj DW8

was susceptible at AICRIP but resistant at the other locations. Ptb 18, also susceptible at AICRIP, was resistant or intermediate at the other locations. Hence, the strain of the rice tungro virus at AICRIP might be more virulent. Habiganj DW8 and Ptb 18 could be used to separate the tungro strain at AICRIP (if it remains stable) from strains at other locations. ■

Perpetuation of rice tungro virus and its vectors

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The possibility that improved rice cultivars, stubble, wild rices, weeds, and cereal crops can act as reservoir host for rice tungro virus and that wild rices, weeds, and cereal crops are host for the tungro virus *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus* was investigated. Both standing crops and stubble of the cultivars Bala, IR8, Krishna, Padma, and TN1 served as better sources of virus inoculum. The cultivars that served as poor inoculum sources were IR20, IR30, Annapurna, IR26, Ratna, CR 138-802-10, and CR 138-994-27.

The susceptible wild rice species were *Oryza australiensis*, *O. barthii*, *O. brachyantha*, *O. eichingeri*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, and *O. perennis*. Of these *O. barthii*, *O. nivara*, and *O. glaberrima* served as better sources of

virus inoculum than the others when tested at 15, 30, 35, 60, 75, and 90 days after inoculation (see table).

The resistant wild rice species were *O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, *O. latifolia*, *O. malampzhuensis*, *O. minuta*, *O. officinalis*, *O. perreiri*, and *O. schwenforthiana*. None of the 20 weed species and 6 cereal crops tested was susceptible to tungro virus.

The vector species *N. nigropictus* had a broader spectrum of host range than *N. virescens*. *N. nigropictus* could reproduce in *O. eichingeri*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. malampzhuensis*, *O. minuta*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinales*, *O. perennis*, *O. punctata*, *O. sativa*, *Echinochloa colonurn*, *Ischaemum indicum*, *Leersia hexandra*, and *Paspalum orbiculare*. *N. virescens* could reproduce in *O. glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, *O. perennis*, *O. sativa*, *E. colonum*, and *P. orbiculare*.

Intensive cultivation of semidwarf rice cultivars has made the overlapping of two crops of rice a common practice. Such circumstances might cause greater

Virus recovery from tungro-susceptible *Oryza* spp. Cuttack, India

<i>Oryza</i> spp.	% viruliferous insects					
	Days after inoculation					
	15	30	45	60	75	90
<i>O. australiensis</i>	0.0	6.7	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>O. harthii</i>	8.3	10.0	20.0	50.0	35.0	14.3
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	0.0	1.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	0.0	0.0	0.0	13.8	5.2	0.0
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	43.5	61.9	66.7	54.5	79.3	38.9
<i>O. nivara</i>	55.0	33.3	46.1	65.4	39.1	60.0
<i>O. perennis</i>	0.0	6.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>O. punctata</i>	0.0	11.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>O. sativa</i>	73.1	68.2	63.3	71.4	47.4	53.3

survival and propagation of tungro virus in the semidwarfs, their stubble, and in wild rice. Some weed hosts such as *E. colonum* might also act as link hosts between two crops, especially in places where a single crop is grown per year.

Although both species of tungro vectors are found together in the paddy ecosystem, they differ in preference for survival and multiplication. It has been

found that rice is a preferred host for *N. virescens* over weeds, whereas *N. nigropictus* prefers weeds (e.g. *L. hexandra*) to rice. Thus, in areas where cropping systems overlap, *N. virescens* might be playing a greater role in tungro perpetuation. In single cropping areas, *N. nigropictus* might transmit tungro virus among weeds or wild rices during the off-season. ■

transplanting. Infection at younger stages of rice growth resulted in complete yield loss.

The brown planthopper transmitted the disease with a latent period of 7 days (range, 3-14 days) at 28-30°C, and infectivity persisted throughout the insects' life. The active transmitters ranged from 22 to 64%. The shortest acquisition access time was 2 hours and the shortest inoculation access time was 30 minutes. Among other Homopteran rice pests so far tested, none transmitted the disease. The disease was not transmitted through rice seeds or by mechanical means. ■

Food web of the rice brown planthopper in the Philippines

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The natural enemy relationships (food web) for the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (BPH) were determined to learn more about the biological control possibilities against that pest. Records of predator-parasite relationships representing 74 taxa were determined over a 2-year period (1977-79) from 4 Philippine provinces representing different rice environments: Los Baños, Laguna (irrigated wetland); Tanauan, Batangas (dryland); Oton, Iloilo, and Manaoag, Pangasinan (rainfed wetland). Parasites were reared on BPH, and predator records of field observations or cage studies were obtained. Specimens were sent to taxonomists worldwide for species confirmation. A list of the specialists is available on request.

Five egg parasites belonging to Mymaridae and Trichogrammatidae were recorded (see figure). *Anagrus*, a mymarid species, was the most common. *Gonotocerus*, a mymarid egg parasite of BPH recorded elsewhere in Asia, is host to the green leafhopper *Nephotettix* spp. and was never reared from BPH eggs.

Rice wilted stunt in Taiwan

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A rice disease characterized by extreme plant stunting, narrow leaves, and, often, premature death of infected plants was first found in paddy fields of Tungshih, central Taiwan in 1977 (see photo). Leaf wilting usually occurred first in the outer, older, leaves, and gradually proceeded to the upper leaves, resulting in plant death at later tillering stages. The disease was transmissible by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, the vector of rice grassy stunt and rice ragged stunt. The frequently lethal symptoms appear to distinguish the disease from grassy stunt and ragged stunt. The disease was named rice wilted stunt and is possibly a new virus disease of rice (see photo).

In greenhouse tests, seedlings of Tainan 5, a japonica, produced rusty yellowish leaves at about 10 days after inoculation. Young leaves twisted and turned pale green. Because the diseased

Rice wilted stunt on Taichung Sen 3. Healthy (right) and infected (left) plants, 60 days after inoculation.

plants seemed weak and usually had fewer tillers than normal, they appear similar to plants infected with rice transitory yellowing virus. Yield losses for Tainan 5 were 95, 78, 73, 65, and 40% when the disease symptoms were first expressed at 21-30, 31-40, 41-50, 51-60, and 61-70 days after transplanting. The yield reduction was 97, 82, and 77% for Taichung sen 3, an indica, when the symptoms were first expressed at 21-30, 31-40, and 41-50 days after